

Interface Interaction in Aluminum-Carbon System

M. Kh. Shorshorov, T. A. Chernyshova, L. I. Kobeleva

Baikov Institute of Metallurgy, Moscow, B-334 Prospect Lenina, 49 USSR

ABSTRACT

Samples of a composite material were obtained by compressive infiltration of a carbon tape by Al-12 wt.% Si melt. Morphology of the carbide phase (Al_4C_3) being formed on the fibre-matrix interface boundary during infiltration and its effect on the material strength were investigated. Increase of the contact time of a fibre with the melt, melt temperature and infiltration pressure leads to the growth of the carbide phase quantity and bond strength along the fibre-matrix interface. Here the nature of fracture under tensile test varies from ductile - with noticeable fibres pulling out of the matrix up to brittle one; shear strength rises. Maximum tensile strength was obtained on samples with the fracture of the intermediate type; relation of the length of pulled out fibres to their diameter is about 100. The quantity of the carbide phase in these samples is 13,8 mg of Al_4C_3 per 1 g of the carbon fibre, the average size of the carbide phase crystals is about 0,1 μm and the average distance between them was $\sim 1,0 \mu m$.

INTRODUCTION

Formation of the carbide phase in the composite material (CM) aluminium-carbon and its effect on mechanical properties of CM are studied in detail conformably to isothermal annealing (1-3). It has been shown that growth of aluminium carbides on the interface leads to lowering of CM strength. CM strength decrease providing heat treatment above 500°C was marked in (2). Heat treatment of individual fibres with aluminium coating during 100 hours reduces their strength about 30% in case of high strength fibres (annealing under 475°C) and 45% of fibres are high modulus (annealing under 550°C); strength lowering is more noticeable under increasing the thickness of the aluminium coating controlling the length of an initial crack in the brittle interlayer (3).

There are no as a rule data on carbide formation under CM production, on production method effect on quantity and morphology of the carbide phase. By the way unstability of carbon-aluminium

CM properties is probably connected with uncontrolled formation of Al_4C_3 carbide exactly under CM production.

Due to this the purpose of the present investigation was to determine morphology of the interaction products on the interface boundaries under CM production by the solid-phase method, to analyze the character of the bond between a fibre and the matrix, to determine the concentration of the carbide phase that provides the maximum strength of the carbon-aluminium CM.

MATERIAL AND METHODS OF INVESTIGATION

Investigations were carried out on CM samples obtained by vacuum-compression infiltration of a carbon tape by Al-12% Si alloy. Tensile strength of the tape filament was 2600 MPa, the coefficient of elasticity 26700 MPa. Content of fibres in the filaments was equal to about 55%.

Compositions quality was evaluated according to fracture character, results of tensile tests and interlayer shear under three-point bending. Tests were carried out on flat samples of $2 \times 10 \times 4.5$ mm varying L_s basis. Shear strength was determined by the relation $L_s/d \leq 5$ ($d^s = 2$ mm - diameter of the bending punch), tensile strength - by $L_s/d \geq 15$ (4).

It is not managed to reveal products of interaction of a fibre with the matrix by methods of light microscopy but is possible to detect under investigation of extracted carbon replicas from fractures and the lateral surface of fibres etched from the matrix using electron microscopes. Electronograms were made from the particles extracted into carbon replicas. To preserve carbides on the fibres the silumin matrix was dissolved in a waterless organic solvent. The quantitative chemical analysis was used to determine the content of the carbide phase in the CM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Compressive infiltration of carbon fibres promotes satisfactory occupation of interfibre spaces by silumin. Metallographic edges of the samples exhibit presence of a matrix between plaits and in capillars inside the plaits (Fig.1).

Carbon replicas reveal fine fraction cleavage of the carbon fibres, places of ductile or quasi-ductile matrix fracture. The interaction products are found on the interface boundaries as isolated particles with arbitrary orientation in relation of the fibre and germinating to the matrix side (Fig.2a). Being extracted into a replica the particles are identified as the Al_4C_3 carbide (Fig.2b) using electronography.

Particles of the aluminium carbide are found on the fibres etched out of the matrix as flat six-angle plates with chaotic distribution on the surface (Fig.3). On the fibres of one plait and sometimes in the range of one elementary fibre parallel with colonies of densely distributed Al_4C_3 plates there are found places with separate crystals and also places free from the carbide crystals. Such irregularity of the carbides formation is probably connected with nonhomogeneous structure of the carbon fibres surface. Besides, it is possible to suppose that silicium containing in silumin segregates on the interface and reduces so the probability of Al_4C_3 phase formation.

At first the carbide particles grow into the matrix (Fig.3d),

then at late stages of reaction interaction their inclusion into the fibre occurs. This is also exhibited by pits on the lateral side of the fibre after the carbide fracture.

Increasing the infiltration and contact time of a fibre with the melt leads to growth of the carbides and formation of new ones. The continuous layer of the aluminium carbide on the fibre is not observed under the chosen conditions of infiltration by silumin. The layer formation may be prevented both by silicium segregation on the fibre-matrix interface and growth of the silicium crystals from the fibre surface deep into the matrix by silumin crystallization (Fig.4).

Stresses transfer from the fibre to the matrix is realised through the carbide phase. The fractographic analysis has shown that fracture of such "cohesion bridges" occurs along the carbide-fibre boundary. The aluminium carbides are not found on the lateral side of the fibres pulled out of the matrix (Fig.5). The components interaction on the interface between inclusions of the carbide phase is not observed. Consequently, it may be considered that in the result of physicochemical interaction in the carbon-aluminium composition the super-position of two types of the bond between the fibre and the matrix - mechanical and reaction - takes place (5).

Quantitative chemical analysis has shown that increase of infiltration pressure leads to rising of concentration of the carbide phase in samples. It is probably connected with increase of the contact surface between the melt and the fibre and mechanical activation of the fibre surface. Under high temperatures of infiltration the dependence of the carbide phase quantity on the pressure is more prominent. Increasing of infiltration temperature, time of interaction of the fibre with the melt also leads to growth of Al_4C_3 quantity in the composition (Fig.6). In the result the interaction on the interface improves.

Depending on the bond strength on the fibre-matrix interface in carbon-aluminium CM there are observed three main types of fracture under tensile test along the reinforcing direction: brittle, tensile and intermediate (6,7). It is characteristic for samples with large quantity of the carbide phase to exhibit brittle fracture with development of the main crack in a plane normal to reinforcing fibres and $l/d < 10$ (Fig.7a) (l - length of fibres pulled out of the matrix, d - diameter of fibres). In points of plaits infiltration a brittle crack may be transferred from filament to filament through inosculated carbide crystals. Under a weak interface interaction the so called ductile fracture is being formed with strong fibres pulling out or crack branching in the reinforcing direction, $l/d > 300$ (Fig.7b). $l/d \approx 100$ (Fig.7c) is for the fracture of intermediate type (splintery).

Mechanical properties of the silumin-carbon fibres composition were studied under various infiltration conditions. Fig.8 illustrates the results of CM samples bend test depending on the fracture type or the l/d parameter. It is shown that with increasing of the carbide phase the shear strength rises. The tensile strength is described by the curve with maximum corresponding to $l/d \approx 100$. The chemical analysis has shown that quantity of the carbide phase in such CM reaches 13,8 mg of Al_4C_3 per 1 g of the carbon fibre. Here the average diameter of the carbide phase crystals (Al_4C_3) is equal to about $10^{-1} \mu m$, the average distance between carbides inclusions is equal to about $1,0 \mu m$.

CONCLUSION

Morphology of Al_4C_3 carbide phase in the carbon fibres-silumin composition has been investigated depending on vacuum-compression infiltration. The samples which fractures are characterized by relation of the length of fibres pulled out of the matrix to the fibres diameter as $l/d \approx 100$ exhibit the best mechanical properties. The quantity of the aluminium carbide in such composition is equal to 13,8 mg of Al_4C_3 per 1 g of the carbon fibre.

REFERENCES

- 1 Blankenbergs, C. "The Effect of Carbide Formation on the mechanical behaviour of Carbon-Aluminium Composites", J. Australian Institute of Metals, vol.14, No.4, 1969, pp.236-241.
- 2 Khan, I.H. "The Effect of Thermal Exposure on the Mechanical properties of Aluminium-Graphite Composites", Met.Trans., Sept., Vol.7A, No.9, 1977, pp.1928-1989.
- 3 Baker, S.I., Bonfield, W. "Fracture of Aluminium-Coated Carbon Fibres", J. of Mater.Sci., Vol.13, No. 6, 1978, pp.1329-1334.
- 4 Ignatowitz, E. Zur Herstellung eines Kohlenstoffaserverstärkten Aluminium, Verbundwerkstoffs, Dissertation, Universität, Karlsruhe, 1973.
- 5 Metcalf, A., Clayn, M. "Interface Effect on Mechanical Properties of Composites under Longitudinal Tension", Interface Surfaces in Metallic Composites. Composite Materials, vol.1., Trans. from Eng. / Ed. I.I.Svetlov, Moscow, Mir, 1978, pp.137-184.
- 6 Shorshorov, M.Kh., Shernyshova, T.A., Savvateeva, S.M., Kobeleva, L.I. "Technological Coatings in the Silumin-Carbon Fibre Composition Obtained by Liquid-Phase Method", Fizika i khimiy obrabotki materialov, No.4, 1980, pp.124-130.
- 7 Shorshorov, M.Kh., Kolpashnikov, A.I., Kostikov, V.I., Shernyshova, T.A. et al. Fibre Composite Materials with Metallic Matrix / Ed. M.Kh. Shorshorov. Moscow, Mashinostroenie, 1981, 272 p.

Fig.1. Structure of the composite material - Al-Si alloy.

a

b

Fig.2. Replica from the transverse bending of CM (a) and electronogram from the marked indentation cup (b). 1 - a fibre; 2 - a matrix.

a

b

c

Fig.3. Surface of the carbon fibres with the aluminium carbides.

a

b

Fig.4. Silicium crystals on the surface of the carbon fibres.
a) - metallographic edge; b) fibres after chemical cleaning of aluminium in the solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 + \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$.

Fig.5. Fractography of the CM sample - silumin-carbon fibre.

Fig.6. Dependence of Al_4C_3 quantity in the CM on pressure (a), temperature (b) and infiltration time (c).

Fig.7. Fracture surfaces of the samples after mechanical tests: a - brittle fracture, b - fracture with a strong branching of a crack, c - intermediate type of fracture.

Fig.8. Dependence of the mechanical properties of the silumin-carbon tape composition on bending type.

